

Ride 2Rail

D6.3 RIDE2RAIL Project Leaflet

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report describes the objectives, structure and look and feel of the RIDE2RAIL leaflet. The leaflet is considered an essential tool within the project to reach objectives concerning communication, including strengthening the RIDE2RAIL identity, raising awareness, and disseminating project objectives to key stakeholders and external actors.

Currently, the RIDE2RAIL leaflet is available in electronic format, but as soon as face-to-face events will take place again, the leaflet will be printed too.

Abbreviations and acronyms

CFM	Calls for Members
DL	Dissemination and exploitation leader
DoA	Description of the Action
EL	Ethical leader
EU	European Union
FS	Financial Statement
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
IP4	Innovation Programme 4
OC	Open Call
PC	Project coordinator
PM	Project manager
PMO	Project Management Office
PMT	Project Management Team
PO	Project Officer
QAC	Quality Assurance Committee
S2R JU	Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking
TL	Technical leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work package leader

2. BACKGROUND

The present document constitutes the Deliverable D6.3 “Leaflet” in the framework of the WP6, task 6.1 of the RIDE2RAIL project.

3. OBJECTIVES/AIM

One of the objectives of the RIDE2RAIL communication activities is to raise awareness and disseminate project objectives and developments to key stakeholders and external actors. The RIDE2RAIL leaflet is an important tool developed to reach this objective.

The project leaflet, which follows the earlier developed RIDE2RAIL graphic identity in terms of colour scheme and fonts, has been developed to further advance a strong project identity. A strong identity evokes recognition among stakeholders, ensures consistency in communication activities, and positions the RIDE2RAIL project as a strong brand.

The RIDE2RAIL leaflet will be shared through various digital channels such as the RIDE2RAIL website and social media. Furthermore the leaflet will be shared (hereby taking into account any further deviations due to the COVID-19 crisis) through face-to-face events organised or attended by RIDE2RAIL.

The RIDE2RAIL leaflet can be found in Annex 1 of this document, and on the RIDE2RAIL website, via the link <https://ride2rail.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/Ride2Rail-Tri-fold-final-web.pdf>.

4. LEAFLET

Design of leaflet

The leaflet has been designed by an external agency, after careful briefing by UITP on requirements and wishes. As mentioned in Chapter 3, the RIDE2RAIL leaflet has been designed according to the RIDE2RAIL visual identity, which includes specific use of colour schemes and fonts. It was decided to keep the look and feel of the leaflet clean and modern, to reflect the innovative nature of the project. This is also reflected on the leaflet's cover (Figure 1).

For the cover, the image follows the visuals used for the RIDE2RAIL website, to ensure consistency among the different tools created in the project. Alongside the picture, the project logo is clearly depicted. Finally, the EU emblem and Shift2Rail logo, as well as the grant agreement number, have been included at the bottom.

Figure 1: RIDE2RAIL leaflet cover

Content of the leaflet

One of the requirements of the RIDE2RAIL leaflet is that it should be understandable for all stakeholders interested in the project: from (public) transport experts, to authorities, to citizens. This is reflected in the way the content is written: free from jargon, in a clear and straight-forward way.

The main text in the leaflet is divided into three headings, each looking at the project from a different angle:

- The why (Integrating ride-sharing with public transport)
- The where (Demo sites)
- The what and how (Objectives)

Figure 2: RIDE2RAIL leaflet inside pages

To reflect the fact that RIDE2RAIL is not a stand-alone project, but that it rather connects to other Shift2Rail JU IP4 projects, a dedicated section was included (Figure 3) to explain in a clear way how RIDE2RAIL fits into the IP4 ecosystem.

At the top of this page, some key facts & figures about the project have also been listed.

Figure 3: RIDE2RAIL leaflet - IP4 context & key figures

Last but not least, the backcover of the leaflet (Figure 4) includes information about the different Consortium partners and it also provides the references to the project website and Twitter account, along with the coordinator’s contact details,.

CONSORTIUM

The RIDE2RAIL consortium consists of 17 partners from 10 countries, covering the whole urban mobility chain.

CONTACT

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Figure 4: RIDE2RAIL leaflet backcover

5. CONCLUSIONS

By developing the project leaflet, another essential step towards a coherent and consistent project identity has been made. By following the project's visual guidelines, the brand of RIDE2RAIL was supported with the creation of the leaflet. Additionally, by including information in the leaflet that is free of jargon and therefore understandable for all stakeholders, the leaflet has the capacity to speak to every target audience. The leaflet also gives the readers clear guidance for those who want to know more about the RIDE2RAIL developments, by highlighting the project's website and Twitter account and by providing the coordinator's contact details.

From its launch, the project leaflet will serve as a central tool to engage with relevant audiences and to increase interest into RIDE2RAIL and its mission to further integrate ride-sharing with public transport.

6. ANNEXES

Annex 1: RIDE2RAIL leaflet

Ride 2Rail

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INTEGRATING RIDE-SHARING WITH PUBLIC TRANSPORT

Ride-sharing is considered by many as a potential solution to reduce the number of private cars on our roads and advance sustainable mobility. But even with recent mobile technologies facilitating ride-sharing, this way of travelling has demonstrated limited uptake due to reasons including insufficient awareness of available services, lack of willingness to ride with strangers and uncertainty in reaching agreements on sharing costs.

The RIDE2RAIL project aims to develop solutions and tools that will facilitate the efficient combination of ride-sharing and scheduled transport services such as bus and rail.

In the RIDE2RAIL vision, ride-sharing is a "feeder" for public transport, particularly in rural and low density areas. This makes it a more attractive alternative compared to the private car, which is often occupied by only one person.

By making it easier to compare and choose between multiple transport options and services, RIDE2RAIL seeks to make ride-sharing a (more) attractive way to move passengers to public transport services and at the same time fight congestion and pollution.

DEMO SITES

Offering a seamless experience of multimodal travel is the key to promote the modal shift towards public and shared mobility and promote sustainable mobility.

To achieve this, customers need to feel in control of their own trip and public transport needs to be easy to use and as flexible as possible.

To test how and where RIDE2RAIL shall reach these goals, project solutions will be demonstrated in four areas in Europe, in both urban and rural contexts.

OBJECTIVES

Develop an innovative framework for intelligent mobility, to facilitate the efficient combination of flexible and scheduled transport services and integrate real-time information about public transport and ride sharing.

Create a tool that facilitates the comparison and the choice between multiple services classified by a set of criteria, for example environmental, travel time, comfort, cost.

Encourage carpooling (and ride sharing acceptance) as complementary for public transport.

Enhance performance of the overall mobility system, reduce road congestion and environmental impact, reinforce the mobility offer in rural and low-demand areas.

Combine travel offer classifications and software components and integrate them into existing transport services.

Produce recommendations for replicability.

RIDE2RAIL IN BRIEF

Duration:
December 2019 - May 2022

Budget:
€3 million

Coordinator:
UITP (International Association of Public Transport)

RIDE2RAIL AS PART OF SHIFT2RAIL'S INNOVATION PROGRAMME

RIDE2RAIL falls under the fourth Innovation Programme (IP4) from the Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking, which addresses the subject of IT Solutions for Attractive Railway Services. RIDE2RAIL is complementary to the ongoing IP4 projects CONNECTIVE, COHESIVE, and MaaSive. Together, they aim to tackle in the best possible way the challenges of the IP4 services ecosystem.

CONSORTIUM

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